

The temperature dependence of the impedance spectrum of the barium crystal glass

Katarína Faturíková¹, Marek Liška^{2,3}, Peter Višcor⁴

¹ Central Laboratories, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

² VILA – Joined Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

³ VILA, FunGlass, A. Dubcek University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

⁴ EIS Laboratory, Skjoldenaesvej 17, 4174 Jystrup, Denmark

ABSTRACT

Electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) technique is a non-destructive powerful technique for the characterization of the electrical behavior of material. This technique can be used as electrical characterization tool in materials research and development when studying defects, microstructure, surface chemistry, electrical conductivity and electrical permittivity for a wide range materials, including dielectrics and ionic conductors and to study various polarization processes as a function of applied external electric field. The technique involves the measurement of the sinusoidal component of the current flowing through the sample, resulting from the sinusoidal voltage, applied across two terminals of a sample [1, 2, 3].

A comprehensive Electrical Impedance Spectroscopy study of the electrical response of barium crystal glass has been undertaken in order to determine various electrically active physical processes taking place in this system. The temperature dependence of the impedance spectra of the barium crystal glass was studied in an interval from 50°C to 400°C with step 50°C, in the frequency range from 1mHz to 1 MHz. Samples with thickness 0,7mm, 1mm, 1,7mm and 2,5mm were studied.

Investigations of the relaxation processes in dielectric materials are usually restricted to an analysis of the frequency dependences of the real (ϵ') and imaginary (ϵ'') parts of the complex dielectric permittivity $\epsilon = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$ [4, 5].

In this contribution the temperature and thickness dependence of the dc conductivity and the distribution of relaxation times of dielectric relaxation will be presented and shortly discussed.

Keywords: electrical impedance spectroscopy, dielectric properties, barium glass, distribution of relaxation times

References:

- [1] NITSCH, K.: Microelectronic materials and structures characterization by impedance spectroscopy. Microelectronics reliability, vol. 51, 2011. p. 1213-1218.
- [2] MICKA, K.: Introduction into the theory of impedance measurements. Praha: VŠCHT, 2001, ISBN 80-7080-228-6.
- [3] BARSOUKOV, E., MACDONALD, J.R.: Impedance spectroscopy: Theory, Experiment and Applications, New Jersey: Wiley, 2005. ISBN 0-471-64749-7.
- [4] Turík A. V., Rodinin M. Yu. Dielectric Losses in Materials with Limited Range of Relaxation Times. Technical Physics Letters, 2010; 36; 16–18.
- [5] Constantino Grosse. A program for the fitting of Debye, Cole–Cole, Cole–Davidson, and Havriliak–Negami dispersions to dielectric data. Journal of Colloid and Interface Science. 2014; 419; 102–106.

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

This work was supported by The Slovak Grant Agency for Science under grant No. VEGA 2/0088/16, VEGA 1/0064/18 and APVV 0487-11.